

Correction of the Error in Electromagnetic Theory

Part 2

The Relationship Between Doppler Shift, Signal Speed, and Wave Mechanics

Han Erim
Independent Researcher

8 December 2025

E-mail: hanerim@aliceinphysics.com

Web: www.aliceinphysics.com

I – SUMMARY

In this study, using the Doppler Shift, it is demonstrated that the speed of an electromagnetic wave (signal) varies according to reference frames.

The main findings of the study can be summarized as follows:

- **From the perspective of the Target Object**, the speed of a signal arriving at or approaching it is **always constant and equal to “c”** in the Target Object’s own reference frame.
- **When there is relative motion between the Source Object and the Target Object**, the speed of the signal emitted by the Source Object in its own reference frame is **different from “c” value**.
- **In the Doppler Shift, the change in wavelength** occurs at the **moment the signal is emitted**, and is **independent of the distance** between the Source and Target Objects.
- In the Doppler Shift, **the change in wavelength** and **the change in emission speed of the signal** occur **simultaneously** in accordance with wave mechanics.
Emitted Signal Speed = Signal frequency × Modified wavelength of the signal

These results show that there are various deficiencies and errors in Electromagnetic Theory. The presented study makes corrections to these deficiencies and brings Electromagnetic Theory to a more consistent and explanatory level.

II – METHOD AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In the explanation of this study, a signal transmitter device that generates a homogeneous and uniform electromagnetic wave has been used. The frequency of the device is assumed to be constant and f_0 . With this frequency value, the wavelength of the sinusoidal signals produced by the device will be, according to the equation $c = f_0 \cdot \lambda_0$. Therefore, the values f_0 and λ_0 are accepted as the basic factory characteristics of the device. It is assumed that all signal transmission operations considered in the study are carried out with these fixed-frequency signal generators. One of these devices is placed on the aircraft, and the others on the signal towers.

Figure 1 – Device used in the study.

Information note:

All figures used in this article are created from frames taken from the relevant animations. The star symbol (★) in the figure descriptions indicates that the relevant figure has a watchable animation.

You can view the full version of the article, together with its animated version, on my personal website: www.aliceinphysics.com

Experimental Setup:

In the First Section of the explanation:

As seen in Figure 2 below, there is a tower at position O in the center, and two side towers at positions A and B on both sides.

Figure 2 – The tower at position O in the center sends signals to the towers at A and B.

In Figure 3, there is an aircraft passing over position O, and again towers are located at positions A and B in the same way.

Figure 3 – As the aircraft passes over position O, it begins to send signals to the towers A and B.

The distances of the side towers A and B to position O are equal to each other. In the study, first signals were sent from the central tower to the side towers A and B, and then signals were sent from the aircraft to the towers A and B, and the two situations were compared; the wavelength changes due to the Doppler Shift and the signal speeds were examined based on these comparisons.

In the Second Section of the explanation:

As seen in Figure 4, this time signals were sent from the side towers A and B to the aircraft in the middle, and again the wavelength change and signal speeds arising due to the Doppler Shift were examined.

Figure 4 – As the aircraft passes over position O, the towers A and B begin to send signals.

In order to clearly see how the formation of the Doppler Shift and the signal speeds differ according to the source and target reference frames, the motion of the towers and the aircraft has been chosen to be along the same line. In this way, it has been made more evident which physical quantities the changes in wavelength and wave speed arise from.

III – EXPLANATION OF THE SUBJECT AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE EVENT (First Section)

1) Signal is sent from the Central Tower

The tower at the central position **O** sends signals to the towers **A** and **B**, which are at equal distances from it.

Figure 5 – The central tower sends signals to the side towers.

Development of the event:

- The tower starts to send the signal at moment t_1 .
- The signals moving in both directions reach the side towers at moment t_2 .
- Travel time of the signal: $t = t_2 - t_1$
- The distances covered by the signals going to the right and left
Since the signal speed is “ c ”: $AO = BO = c \cdot t$
- Representation of the covered distances in terms of wavelength:
The source and target towers are motionless relative to each other. Therefore, there is no change in the wavelength of the signal, and the fixed wavelength value λ_0 of the device remains valid.

Therefore, the distance covered is:

$$AO = BO = \lambda_0 \cdot n$$

The value of n :

$$n = \frac{c \cdot t}{\lambda_0}$$

Since the towers are motionless relative to each other, the wavelength of the signal will not change here.

In Figure 6 below, the arrival moment of the signals and the related mathematical equations are shown. (This figure can be seen in enlarged form on Page 6 – Figure 8.)

Figure 6 (★) – The signals sent by the central tower have reached the towers on both sides.

2) Sending Signals from the Aircraft to the Towers

At time t_1 , the aircraft passing over point **O** begins to send signals to the towers on both sides. The speed of the aircraft is taken as “ v ”.

Figure 7 – The aircraft sends signals to the side towers.

Due to the motion of the aircraft, it is clearly observed that the wavelengths of the signals change. In the animated version of the figure, this situation can be seen clearly without any explanation.

- The wavelengths of the signals going toward the A tower behind the aircraft are stretched and shown as λ_1 .
- The wavelengths of the signals going toward the B tower in front of the aircraft are shortened and shown as λ_2 .

Summary of the sequence of events:

At moment t , when the aircraft is at position **O**, the signal emission begins.

- Since the signals set out from position **O**, they arrive at the towers A and B, which are at equal distances from point **O**, at the same moment t_2 .
- Travel time of the signals: $t = t_2 - t_1$
- At the initial moment of the event, t_1 , the aircraft is at position **O**. During the time until the signals reach the towers, the aircraft moves with speed v and at moment t_2 it **arrives at position C**.
The distance covered by the aircraft during this time: $OC = v \cdot t$
- The aircraft emits signals in both directions with **the same frequency**. Therefore, the numbers of wave trains formed in both directions are equal. This number is denoted by “**n**” in the figure.

- **In the reference frame of the aircraft itself**, the paths covered by the signals sent to the towers are shown as follows:

Signal going to the left side (toward tower A):

Tower A is receding from the aircraft with speed v . In this case, the path covered by the signal going to tower **A**:

$$\text{In terms of speed and time: } AC = c \cdot t + v \cdot t = (c + v) \cdot t$$

$$\text{In terms of wavelength: } AC = n \cdot \lambda_1$$

Signal going to the right side (toward tower B):

Tower B is approaching the aircraft with speed v . In this case, the path covered by the signal going to tower **B**:

$$\text{In terms of speed and time: } BC = c \cdot t - v \cdot t = (c - v) \cdot t$$

$$\text{In terms of wavelength: } BC = n \cdot \lambda_2$$

In the figure below, the arrival moments of the signals at the towers **A** and **B** and the related mathematical equations are shown.

At this point, **we can clearly see the fundamental error made in Electromagnetic Theory**. According to Electromagnetic Theory, the speed of electromagnetic signals sent from a source must always be “**c**”, regardless of which reference frame is considered. According to the ground reference frame and the reference frames of the side towers **A** and **B**, the fact that the speed of the signals is “**c**” is clearly seen in the figure and is beyond dispute. **In contrast, when we move to the reference frame of the aircraft, the physical picture changes completely**. In the reference frame of the aircraft, the speed of the signals going to tower **A** becomes “**c+v**”, and the speed of the signals going to tower **B** becomes “**c-v**”. Taking into account that the travel time of the signals to towers **A** and **B** is $t = t_2 - t_1$, the signal speeds in the reference frame of the aircraft are easily calculated:

In the reference frame of the aircraft:

The speed of the signals going to tower **A**: $c_1 = \frac{AC}{t} = c + v$ $c_1 = \frac{AC}{t} = c + v$

The speed of the signals going to tower **B**: $c_2 = \frac{BC}{t} = c - v$ are obtained.

Therefore, the fact that the speeds of the signals sent by the aircraft become $c \pm v$ instead of c constitutes a clear contradiction with the electromagnetic theory, which asserts that the speed of light must be constant in all reference frames. This result shows that the theory does not correctly reflect reality at a very critical point.

Figure 8 (★) – The signals transmitted by the aircraft reach the side towers.

Another important finding revealed by the graph is this: All the signals going to the left side have the same wavelength (λ_1). Similarly, all the signals going to the right side have the wavelength λ_2 .

These changes in wavelength **occur independently** of the characteristic properties of the device emitting the signal and **at the moment the signal is emitted**. In the animation version of the figure, this process can be clearly observed.

The factory settings of the device theoretically satisfy

$$c = f_0 \cdot \lambda_0$$

although this equality holds, assuming that the wavelengths of the signals emitted by the device will always be λ_0 does not reflect the real physical situation. Here λ_0 is only a **reference wavelength**. The physical quantity that determines the change in wavelength is the relative velocity “ v ” between the Source Body and the Target Body.

$$\lambda_x = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c \pm v)}{c}$$

Doppler Shift Equation

As seen in the Doppler Shift equation, the change in wavelength occurs by applying a ratio determined by v . Therefore λ_0 is **the basic reference quantity on which the change occurs**.

Physically, the fact that the relative velocity between the Source Body and the Target Body can take any value means that the wavelengths of the signals produced by the device **may vary in infinite diversity**. The device sends signals not only to the towers, but simultaneously to many bodies moving at different speeds and in different directions relative to it. Since these signals are produced by the same device, their frequencies remain the same, but their **wavelengths take different values** depending on the relative velocity between the Source and the Target.

When the shapes formed by the signals together in the sky are examined in the figure, it is seen that **homogeneous wave trains** are formed on both sides. This is an expected result because the device operates at a fixed frequency and the aircraft moves in uniform linear motion. At the same time, this appearance reveals a very important physical fact:

“In the Doppler Shift, the change in wavelength occurs during the emission of the signal.”

Taking into account that the change in the signal wavelength occurs at the moment the signals are emitted, it will be easier to understand how extraordinary the physical mechanism we are dealing with really is.

3- Comparison

In Figure 9 below, Figures 6 and 8 are placed one under the other so that they can be seen together for comparison purposes.

- In the upper part, the case where the **aircraft** sends signals to the towers at positions **A** and **B** (Figure 8),
- In the lower part, the case where **the tower at the central position O** sends signals to the side towers (Figure 6) is shown.

Figure 9 (★) – The arrival of the signals sent from the tower and the aircraft at the towers located at positions A and B.

The summary of the sequence of events in Figure 9 is as follows:

- At moment t_1 the tower at position O and the aircraft are aligned, and the signal emission begins exactly at this moment.
- At moment t_2 the signals reach the towers at positions A and B, and at the same moment t_2 the aircraft has reached position C.
- Since both the aircraft and the central tower use the same type of signal generator, during the time interval $t = t_2 - t_1$ both sources emit the same number of waves, namely “n” waves in both directions.
- For the signals sent from the central tower to the side towers, since the towers are at rest relative to each other, the wavelength of these signals does not change and remains λ_0 in both directions. In contrast, for the signals sent from the aircraft, since the aircraft and the towers are in motion relative to each other,
 - the wavelength of the signals going to the left increases $\rightarrow \lambda_1$
 - the wavelength of the signals going to the right decreases $\rightarrow \lambda_2$
 in this way it **changes**.

As can be clearly seen on the figure,

$$\lambda_1 > \lambda_0 > \lambda_2$$

is the ordering that is obtained.

Calculation of signal speeds in the aircraft’s reference frame

Using the quantities given in the figure, the speeds of the signals sent to the A and B towers can be calculated in a very simple way according to the aircraft’s reference frame.

Signal going toward tower A:

Since the **aircraft** and tower **A** are moving away from each other, the distance traveled by the signal $AC = (c + v).t$

Therefore, the speed of the signal going to tower **A** according to the aircraft’s reference frame is:

$$c_1 = c + v = \frac{AC}{t}$$

Signal going toward tower B:

Since the **aircraft** and tower **B** are approaching each other, the distance traveled by the signal:

$$BC = (c - v).t$$

Thus, the speed of the signal going to tower **B** according to the aircraft’s reference frame is:

$$c_2 = c - v = \frac{BC}{t}$$

Basic result:

These results clearly and indisputably show that in the aircraft’s reference frame:

the speed of the signals going to the left tower **A** is $c+v$,

and the speed of the signals going to the right tower **B** is $c-v$.

This finding contradicts the fundamental assumption of electromagnetic theory stating that “the speed of light must always be c in all reference frames,” and shows that this assumption does not fully reflect physical reality.

IV- MATHEMATICAL EQUATIONS

DERIVATION OF THE DOPPLER SHIFT EQUATIONS

It is clearly understood from the following basic fact that the quantities obtained from the figures correctly represent the real behavior of nature:

The equation giving the wavelength change in the Doppler Shift can be directly derived from the geometric and temporal relations in the figures, without the need for any additional information.

Below, using the information provided by Figure 9, the derivation of the Doppler Shift equations is shown.

Signal arrival time:

The arrival time of the signals emitted from the aircraft to the towers at positions A and B:

$$t = t_2 - t_1$$

t_1 : the moment the signal is emitted

t_2 : the moment the signal arrives at the towers

During the time interval t , the aircraft moves with speed v and comes from position O to position C.

Obtaining the wavelength of the signals going from the aircraft to the tower A on the left:

The aircraft and tower A are moving away from each other.

$$AO = \lambda_0 \cdot n$$

$$AC = \lambda_1 \cdot n$$

$$AO = c \cdot t$$

$$AC = c \cdot t + v \cdot t = (c + v) \cdot t$$

$$\frac{AO}{AC} = \frac{\lambda_0 \cdot n}{\lambda_1 \cdot n} = \frac{c \cdot t}{(c + v) \cdot t} \Rightarrow \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_1} = \frac{c}{(c + v)} \Rightarrow \boxed{\lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c + v)}{c}} \quad [1]$$

Doppler Shift

Obtaining the wavelength of the signals going from the aircraft to the tower B on the right:

The aircraft and tower B are approaching each other.

$$BO = \lambda_0 \cdot n$$

$$BC = \lambda_2 \cdot n$$

$$BO = c \cdot t$$

$$BC = c \cdot t - v \cdot t = (c - v) \cdot t$$

$$\frac{BO}{BC} = \frac{\lambda_0 \cdot n}{\lambda_2 \cdot n} = \frac{c \cdot t}{(c - v) \cdot t} \Rightarrow \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_2} = \frac{c}{(c - v)} \Rightarrow \boxed{\lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c - v)}{c}} \quad [2]$$

Doppler Shift

V- VARIOUS MEANINGS OF THE DOPPLER SHIFT EXPRESSION:

In the Doppler Shift equation, the speed term v represents the **relative speed** between the Source Body and the Target Body. In this study, in order to analyze how the Doppler Shift equations arise, the motion of the towers and the aircraft has been chosen along the same straight line. For this reason, the value v , which is the speed of the aircraft, appears directly in the Doppler Shift expression.

The Doppler Shift can be interpreted in relation to different physical parameters. These interpretations are presented below under three headings.

1) Interpretation based on relative speed

In this approach, the Doppler Shift expresses the change in the wavelength of the signal as a result of the relative speed between the Source Body and the Target Body. Here, the determining parameter is the value v .

$$\lambda_x = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c \pm v)}{c}$$

λ_x : Modified wavelength

λ_0 : **Original wavelength** of the signal emitted when the Source Body and the Target Body are **at rest with respect to each other**

v : **Relative speed** between the Source Body and the Target Body

c : Speed of light constant

2) Interpretation based on distances (emission–arrival relation)

Here, the parameters are distances. The Doppler Shift equation can be expressed in terms of the distances between the Source Body and the Target Body at the instants of emission and arrival of the signal. Expressing the Doppler Shift in this way:

Wavelength of the signals going to tower A:

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{AC}{AO}$$

Wavelength of the signals going to tower B:

$$\lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{BC}{BO}$$

$t = t_2 - t_1$: signal travel time

$AO = BO = c \cdot t$: Distance between the aircraft and the towers at the moment of emission of the signal

$AC = (c + v) \cdot t$: Distance between the aircraft and tower A at the moment of arrival of the signal

$BC = (c - v) \cdot t$: Distance between the aircraft and tower B at the moment of arrival of the signal

3) Interpretation based on signal speeds

In this interpretation, the determining parameters are the speed values of the signal with respect to the reference frames of the Source Body and the Target Body. The Doppler Shift can be expressed in terms of the relative speed of the emitted signal with respect to the Source Body and the Target Body.

Wavelength of the signals going to tower A:

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{c_1}{c}$$

Wavelength of the signals going to tower B:

$$\lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{c_2}{c}$$

$c_1 = c + v$: Speed of the signal going to tower A according to the aircraft's reference frame.

$c_2 = c - v$: Speed of the signal going to tower B according to the aircraft's reference frame.

c : A and B towers: speed of the signal arriving to them according to their reference frames

VI - REPRESENTATION OF SIGNAL SPEEDS BY WAVE MECHANICS

Even if, in the reference frame of the aircraft, the speed of the signal it emits differs from the value c , Wave Mechanics is still fully preserved in this case as well. It is clearly demonstrated here that the signal speeds $c+v$ and $c-v$, obtained in the reference frame of the aircraft, are in **complete agreement** with Wave Mechanics.

According to Wave Mechanics, the speed of a wave is:

$$\text{Wave speed} = \text{Wavelength} \times \text{Frequency}$$

In the reference frame of the aircraft, it has been obtained in the previous sections that the speed of the signal it sends to the left (towards tower A) is $c+v$, and the speed of the signal it sends to the right (towards tower B) is $c-v$. The speed of the signals sent from the middle tower is " c " and the equality $c = f_0 \cdot \lambda_0$ is satisfied.

1) Wave Mechanics for the signals sent from the aircraft to tower A:

We use the Doppler Shift equation [1] obtained in Section Four (the aircraft and Tower A are moving away from each other).

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c+v)}{c} \Rightarrow \lambda_1 = \frac{c}{f_0} \cdot \frac{(c+v)}{c} \Rightarrow \boxed{c+v = f_0 \cdot \lambda_1} \quad [3]$$

This result shows that the signal going to tower A propagates, in a way consistent with Wave Mechanics, with its frequency, wavelength and speed.

2) Wave Mechanics for the signals sent from the aircraft to tower B

The same procedure is applied here. By using the Doppler Shift equation [2] previously obtained in Section Four (the tower and the aircraft are approaching each other), the result is obtained.

$$\lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c-v)}{c} \Rightarrow \lambda_2 = \frac{c}{f_0} \cdot \frac{(c-v)}{c} \Rightarrow \boxed{c-v = f_0 \cdot \lambda_2} \quad [4]$$

3) Results

As can be clearly seen in the equations [3] and [4] that we have obtained, **if the wavelength of the signal changes at the moment of emission**, then the emission speed of the signal becomes different from the constant “ c ”. It must be especially emphasized here that this speed value is the value of the speed **with respect to the reference frame of the Source Body that emits the signal**.

4) What are the frequencies of the signals coming from the aircraft to the towers, according to the towers?

According to the reference frame of the Target Body to which it will arrive, the speed of a signal coming to it is always constant and equal to c .

The wavelength of the signal arriving at tower A is λ_1 , and the signal has arrived at it with speed c .

Therefore, the frequency of the incoming signal will be:

$$f_1 = \frac{c}{\lambda_1}$$

The wavelength of the signal arriving at tower B is λ_2 , and the signal has arrived at it with speed c .

Therefore, the frequency of the incoming signal will be:

$$f_2 = \frac{c}{\lambda_2}$$

VII - THE PATH TO THE FUTURE OF PHYSICS

At this stage, I would like to talk about a subject that directly concerns the future of physics and will guide the science of physics in the years ahead. Under normal circumstances, such assessments appear at the end of a study, but here I felt the need to make an exception. Because in order to understand the continuation of the topic, we must first demonstrate the existence of a very special and extraordinary situation.

Let us suppose that we are observing a galaxy whose distance is **millions or even billions of light-years away**. In such observations, the **Doppler Shift** always clearly manifests itself. But how is this possible?

As shown in the previous sections, the change in wavelength in the Doppler Shift occurs **at the moment the signal is emitted**. The real meaning of this phenomenon is as follows:

A star in that distant galaxy emits light as if it knew the speed of the Earth relative to itself, adjusting the wavelength of the light it emits so as to satisfy the Doppler Equation.

The electromagnetic signal that leaves the star to travel to the Earth begins its journey, which will last millions/billions of years, with a **modified** wavelength. When the signal reaches the Earth, we measure the wavelength (or frequency) of the signal and, by using the Doppler Shift equation, we calculate whether the star/galaxy is receding from us or approaching us.

The critical point here is this:

The distance between the star and the Earth has no importance whatsoever in this mechanism.

Even if the galaxy were a *billion times a billion light-years* away from us, the Doppler Shift would arise in exactly the same way.

For the Doppler Shift to occur, nature must contain a mechanical infrastructure that determines the wavelength of the signal at the moment of emission and that physically produces the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics in the signal speed. If the universe did not possess such a mechanical infrastructure, the phenomenon called Doppler Shift **could not arise in any way**.

At present, there is no clear information in physics about what this mechanical infrastructure is.

The existing theoretical frameworks tell us how the Doppler Shift is calculated; however, they cannot provide a satisfactory explanation as to why and how this mechanism exists.

The results obtained in this study—that the change in wavelength occurs at the moment of emission and that the signal speed relative to the reference frame of the Source Body can be different from c —add a new depth to the subject of the Doppler Shift. However, this study also does not reveal what this “mechanical infrastructure” is; it only points to its existence in a much stronger and more direct way.

Therefore, before the science of physics stands a great question that will shape future research:

What is the true nature of this hidden mechanism of the universe that makes the Doppler Shift possible?

The answer to this question will be one of the fundamental building blocks that determine the future of physics.

VIII – SUBJECT EXPLANATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE EVENT (SECOND PART)

THE SIDE TOWERS SEND SIGNALS TO THE AIRCRAFT

In the first part of the subject explanation, while demonstrating the formation of the Doppler Shift, the simplest scenario was chosen: Signals are emitted from the aircraft and are sent to the towers that remain stationary at the sides. Since the speed of the signals going to the towers is c in the ground reference frame, there is no physically contradictory situation that could be objected to in this scenario. Thus, the setup can comfortably demonstrate the formation of the Doppler Shift, show that the signal speeds in the reference frame of the aircraft are different from c , and present their relations with wave mechanics. The reason why the signal wavelength changes is also quite understandable when the figures are examined carefully.

In this second part, the flow of events is handled from a different perspective. Here, the towers located on the sides send signals to the aircraft in the middle. **At the initial moment of the event, when the aircraft is at position O, the towers begin to send signals.**

Since the towers and the aircraft are in motion relative to each other, the Doppler Shift will inevitably occur in this case as well. The fundamental question that needs to be answered here is: **Where and how does the change in wavelength occur, and what are the speeds of the signals that the towers send to the aircraft?**

1) Incorrect assumption:

Let us assume that the signals are emitted from the towers in all directions with speed “ c ” (Figure 10). When the signals reach the aircraft, which is moving with speed “ v ”, one may think that an effect in the form of $(c+v)$ and $(c-v)$ will occur depending on the direction of motion of the aircraft. Although this may appear reasonable at first glance, this assumption is not compatible with physical reality.

Because if this assumption is accepted as correct, it would imply that the speed of the signals arriving at the aircraft in its own reference frame is not “ c ”. In this case, **in the aircraft's reference frame**, the speed of the signals arriving from the front would be $c+v$, and the speed of the signals arriving from behind would be $c-v$. This would lead to the following physical contradiction: the aircraft would sense a decrease in energy from signals coming from behind (as implied by $c-v$) and an increase in energy from signals arriving from the front (as implied by $c+v$).

However, in the Doppler Shift, the situation is exactly the opposite. **In the Doppler Shift, $c-v$ represents an increase in energy (wavelength decreases), and $c+v$ represents a decrease in energy (wavelength increases).** Therefore, this assumption is not compatible with nature and cannot explain physical reality.

Figure 10 – The side towers send signals to the aircraft with speed c .

2) Correct Assumption:

If we assume **in the reference frame of the aircraft** that the speed of the signals arriving at it is c and then produce the mathematical solution, we immediately see that the correct result appears. However, this approach has a natural consequence:

The speed of the signals sent by the left A tower to the aircraft, according to the tower's own reference frame, must be $c+v$.

The speed of the signals sent by the right B tower to the aircraft, according to its own reference frame, must be $c-v$. (Figure 11)

In the first part, we found that the speeds of the signals sent from the aircraft to the towers were $c+v$ and $c-v$. Could a similar situation be valid here as well?

Figure 11 – The left tower sends signals to the aircraft with speed $c+v$, and the right tower sends signals with speed $c-v$.

Now let us see that this solution path is indeed correct.

Although we cannot presently explain why the speeds of the signals sent by the towers to the aircraft change (I am referring to the mysterious mechanical infrastructure of the universe O), there is a simple and effective way to prove that this solution path is correct. For this, it is sufficient to refer to the **Galilean Principle of Relativity**. This principle easily shows that this solution is correct and leaves no room for debate.

Galilean Principle of Relativity: The fundamental laws of physics are the same in all reference frames moving at constant velocity relative to each other.

The Galilean Principle of Relativity states that the laws of physics hold in the same way in all reference frames that move without acceleration (at constant velocity). It points to many logical consequences from which we can benefit in physics. By making use of these logical consequences, it is often possible to reach a solid and correct conceptual consistency. Here we will follow the same method. Below are some important results that have been obtained by using this principle and are directly related to our subject.

1) The distinction between moving body and stationary body is not absolute.

Within the logic of physics, if two bodies are in motion relative to each other, the question of “which one is moving and which one is at rest” **has no physical answer**. With respect to a specifically chosen reference frame, we may assume either of these two bodies to be at rest. Such a choice will not produce any difference in the physical processes between the two bodies.

2) Who sends the signal does not change the physical result.

Due to the previous reasoning, in our example of the towers and the aircraft, it should not be important which one sends the signal. The change in the signal wavelength depends on the relative velocity between the Source Body and the Target Body, but it does not depend on which body sends the signal. Since the wavelength of the signal sent by the aircraft to tower A

is λ_1 , the wavelength of the signal sent by tower A to the aircraft will again be λ_1 . Similarly, since the wavelength of the signal going from the aircraft to tower B is λ_2 , the wavelength of the signal that tower B will send to the aircraft will be λ_2 .

3) For a given body, the “speed of the incoming signal” is universally c .

According to the reference frames of towers A and B, the speed of the signal coming to them is constant and equal to c , therefore, in the reference frame of the aircraft, the speed of the signal coming to it must be c .

Is this condition satisfied? It is seen from Figure 11 that this condition is satisfied.

According to the aircraft, the speed of the signal coming to it from tower A: $c = (c + v) - v$

According to the aircraft, the speed of the signal coming to it from tower B $c = (c - v) + v$

4) The mutual arrival times of the signals must be simultaneous.

Since the signals that the aircraft sends to towers A and B reach these towers in time t and simultaneously, the signals that the towers send to the aircraft must also reach the aircraft in time t and simultaneously.

5) The speeds of the signals sent by the towers must be $(c \pm v)$.

According to the reference frame of the aircraft, since the speed of the signal it sends to tower A is $c_1 = c + v = f_0 \cdot \lambda_1$ then, according to the reference frame of tower A, the speed of the signal it sends to the aircraft must also be $c_1 = c + v = f_0 \cdot \lambda_1$. A similar situation exists for tower B. According to the reference frame of tower B, the speed of the signal it sends to the aircraft $c_2 = c - v = f_0 \cdot \lambda_2$ will be.

I believe that these examples are sufficient to demonstrate the logical consistency provided by the Galilean Principle of Relativity. It is also clear how these logical results should correctly appear in the figures and animations: The figure must be constructed so that all the conditions stated above are satisfied, and the mathematical arrangements must be made accordingly.

There is only one solution path that satisfies the conditions completely:

The signals emitted from tower A must be sent to the aircraft with speed $c+v$, and the signals emitted from tower B must be sent with speed $c-v$.

The following figures show two situations.

Figure 12 – The aircraft sends signals to the towers with speeds $(c+v)$ and $(c-v)$.

Figure 13 – The towers send signals to the aircraft with speeds $(c+v)$ and $(c-v)$.

In Figure 14 below, the arrival moments of the signals are shown comparatively.

In the upper part of the figure, the signals are sent from the aircraft; in the lower part, the signals are sent from the side towers.

In both cases the signals have reached their targets. The figure fully satisfies all the conditions required by the Galilean Principle of Relativity.

Figure 14 (★) – Comparative graph prepared using the Galilean Principle of Relativity

When the data obtained from the figure are examined, it is seen that the same mathematical equations are valid in both scenarios.

Thus, the Second Part—which would normally be very difficult to explain—is explained easily by using the Galilean Principle of Relativity, and moreover, without requiring any additional mathematical derivation. If I attempted to explain the second part in the usual way, I would need to write a description consisting of hundreds of pages, and much of what I explained would be lost among theoretical predictions and uncertainties. The Galilean Principle of Relativity is an extremely powerful and fundamental principle in the consistent explanation of physical phenomena.

IX – FINDINGS AND RESULTS

This study has revealed extremely important findings that directly concern the fundamental cornerstones of physical theory. The results obtained are summarized below in itemized form:

1. The physical meaning of the speed of light constant is misunderstood.

The most fundamental finding of this study is as follows:

The speed of light constant “c” represents the speed of a signal that is coming toward an object with respect to the reference frame of that object.

For all bodies, the speed of a signal arriving to them is constant and equal to “c”.

2. The emission speed of the signal with respect to the Source Body is not constant.

In the reference frame of the Source Body, the speed of an emitted signal can take any value depending on which Target Body the signal is traveling to. Due to the relative velocity between the Source Body and the Target Body, the speed of the signal takes a value of the form $c' = c \pm v$. This speed value is also in full agreement with Wave Mechanics.

3. The speeds of signals emitted simultaneously from the Source Body are, in most cases, different from each other.

Let us consider a star as a Source Body. The star simultaneously sends light signals to almost an infinite number of bodies located near it or very far away around it. Almost all of these bodies move with different speeds and in different directions with respect to the star. Therefore, in the reference frame of the Source Body, that is, the star, the speeds of signals that are emitted at the same time but travel to different target bodies will be different from one another.

Consequently, it is not correct to assume that the signals emitted simultaneously from the Source Body are “propagated as the surface of a sphere expanding in space with speed c”. Such a model ignores the fact that, in reality, the signal speeds with respect to the Source Body can take different values such as $c+v$, $c-v$, and therefore it has lost its validity.

In Figures 1, 5, 6, and 7 of the study, spherical drawings depicting the emission of the signals have been deliberately included, although it is known that they are incorrect. Signals are never emitted in the way shown in those figures.

4. The change in wavelength in the Doppler Shift occurs at the Source Body and at the moment of emission.

The magnitude of the change in wavelength is determined by the relative velocity between the Target Body and the Source Body.

As a prediction, I would like to state here that *“in the Doppler Shift process, the Source Body plays a **passive** role, merely generating and emitting the signal; whereas the Target Body plays an **active** role in determining the change in wavelength”*.

5. At the moment a signal is emitted, the Target Body toward which it will travel is physically determined.

The journey of the signal ends when it reaches its target. Electromagnetic radiation is always an interaction that takes place from one body to another; therefore, it is not possible for a signal to be emitted without there being a target body to which it will eventually arrive.

6. These findings clearly show that there is a fundamental deficiency/error in Electromagnetic Theory.

Contemporary Electromagnetic Theory accepts only the constant value c for signal speeds and does not include the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ **mathematics** that we have broadly seen here. Electromagnetic Theory must be reformulated so as to incorporate the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics.

7. When this reformulation is made, there will be no need for the Theory of Special Relativity.

When Electromagnetic Theory fully adopts the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics, it will reach a state in which it can correctly describe the electromagnetic interaction between bodies that are in relative motion with respect to each other.

Such a theoretical structure will already contain within itself all the physical phenomena that the Theory of Special Relativity attempts to explain; therefore, **there will be no need for a separate theory such as the Theory of Special Relativity.**

8) Alice Law is the Electromagnetic Theory that uses the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics.

Since 2001, that is, for almost 25 years, I have been working on the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics. All the studies I have prepared so far I have published under the name Alice Law. In the early years, I was evaluating Alice Law —that is, the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics— on the basis of an alternative theory of relativity. However, over time I understood that this mathematics in fact belongs to Electromagnetic Theory. Therefore today I can comfortably state the following:

Alice Law is the Electromagnetic Theory that uses the $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics.

Just like the Theory of Relativity, Alice Law also has many predictions and results that it points to. For example:

- In Alice Law there are **Time Shift** and **Length Shift**,
- In the Theory of Special Relativity there are **Time Dilation** and **Length Contraction**.

What I am trying to explain here is this:

If you measure that time slows down somewhere, if you see a change in the size of a body, the reason for this is the existence of Alice Law.

Approaching Alice Law with the concepts of the Theory of Relativity is not a correct method. Furthermore, it should not be forgotten that there are significant structural differences between the predictions of the two theories.

You can access all my works related to the predictions and results of Alice Law on my website aliceinphysics.com.

9) The path to the physics of the future.

As Electromagnetic Theory advances on the basis of $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ mathematics, the true physical meaning of the light-speed constant “ c ” will be understood better and it will open the way to discovering that mysterious mechanical infrastructure of the universe which makes this mathematics appear.

X – REFERENCES

- [1] Einstein, A. (1991). *Relativity theory* (G. Aktaş, Trans.). Istanbul, Turkey: Say Yayınları. (Original work published as *Relativity: The Special and the General Theory*)
- [2] Ministry of National Education. (1996). *Physics I for High Schools* (Publication No. 553; Textbook Series No. 168). Ankara, Turkey: Gaye Matbaacılık.
- [3] Erim, H. (2017). *Alice Law – Transition to $(c+v)$ $(c-v)$ Mathematics in Electromagnetic Theory* (Trans. M. H. Kaya; Redaction Y. Özmenekşe). Istanbul, Turkey: Cinius Publishing.
Online publication:
https://www.aliceinphysics.com/publications/alice_law_8/en/index.html
- [4] Erim, H. (2025). *Correction of the Major Error in Electromagnetic Theory and Transition to the Alice Law*.
Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/17667009>
Online publications:
https://www.aliceinphysics.com/publications/alice_law_8/en/part_61.html
- [5] Erim, H. (2025). Erim, H. (2025). *Alice Law – Version 9 Physics Program* [Software].
The program supports Turkish, English, Russian, and Spanish languages.
Access address:
https://www.aliceinphysics.com/download/download_en.html